

A Convolutional Neural Network Model and Algorithm Driven Prototype for Sustainable Tilling and Fertilizer Optimization

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ABSTRACT

Tilling, a common agricultural practice, is being done excessively on farms leading to about 2.35 billion tons of soil erosion from US croplands annually. This causes soil erosion, soil infertility, carbon release, nutrient runoff, and fertilizer over-usage. This paper evaluates whether optimizing tillage intensity, timing, and fertilizer quantity will address these problems. A convolutional neural network based machine learning model utilizes a camera-captured field image to determine existing tilling intensity on a 7-point scale. This machine learning output, along with soil sensor and external forecast data, flows into a 10-parameter algorithm that determines optimal tilling and fertilizer levels. A fully functional tractor prototype demonstrates the above. A 30-year simulation comparing conventionally-tilled and algorithm-tilled farms showed a reduction in carbon emission by 57%, fertilizer usage by 43%, and runoff by 86% demonstrating the transformative potential of this algorithm. Additionally, a stationary prototype was deployed in 155 farms across 5 countries.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the time humans started the disciplined practice of farming, tilling has been viewed as an important piece of the soil preparation phase. However, from the manual plough-handle pressure that farmers applied back in the day to the most sophisticated tilling equipment deployed in modern farms today, the assessment on the tilling level needed has been manually determined based on conventional practices to continuing practices to religiously following what other farmers do (Knowler and Bradshaw, 2007). Science has largely left this assessment of tilling level required “open” leading to potential over-tilling and under-tilling (Derpsch, 2001). In fact, farmers have been over-tilling to maximize yield, which is clearly illustrated by the 2.4 billion tons of soil that is eroded each year from US cropland, with 98% of this loss attributed to overtilling (Borrelli et al., 2017). In addition, studies have found that yields are not impacted due to overtilling (DeFelice et al., 2006).

With farmers focused on maximizing the crop yield, over-tilling and under-tilling come with vast sets of associated problems. The key problems caused by over-tilling are outlined in table 1 below.

Table 1
Negative Effects of Over-Tilling¹

Over-tilling Problem	Description	References
Soil Erosion	Tilling can break up the soil structure, making it more vulnerable to wind and water erosion. This can lead to the loss of precious topsoil, which is vital for plant growth	Basic et al., 2004
Soil Health Degradation	Tilling can disrupt the natural soil structure and harm the beneficial microbes that contribute to soil health	Mikanová et al., 2009
Water and Nutrient Runoff	Disturbed soil from tilling can increase water and nutrient runoff, leading to reduced water infiltration and a higher risk of flooding in certain areas	Barisas et al., 1978
Algae Blooms and ecosystem damage	Runoffs from the field carry nutrients from fertilizer, which can trigger algae blooms when combined with good amounts of sunlight, warm temperatures and slow-flowing water. Harmful algae blooms create	Anderson et al., 2002

toxins that are detrimental to small fish and eventually move up the entire ecological chain

Carbon Release	Soil stores a significant amount of carbon. When tilled, the soil releases this carbon into the atmosphere, contributing to greenhouse gas emissions	Sainju et al., 2008
Moisture Loss	Tilling can cause the soil to dry out more quickly, as the protective surface layer is disturbed, leading to increased evaporation	Blevins et al., 1983
Fuel and Labor Costs	Regular tilling requires machinery, which consumes fuel and may require significant labor, leading to increased costs for farmers	Lithourgidis et al., 2006
Loss of Organic Matter	By exposing organic matter to air and sunlight, tilling can accelerate its decomposition, leading to a reduction in the soil's organic content over time	Franzluebbers, 2004
Potential for Soil Crusting	After tilling, the soil surface can become crusted when exposed to heavy rainfall, making it hard for seedlings to emerge	Mellis et al., 1996

Due to these factors, many farmers and gardeners are adopting no-till or reduced-till practices, which aim to minimize or eliminate the turning of the soil while maintaining or even enhancing soil health and productivity. However zero-tilling and under-tilling or inadequate tilling can also present challenges in certain agricultural contexts. Here are some potential negative effects of under-tilling. Table 2 below outlines the key problems caused by under-tilling.

Table 2
Negative Effects of Under-Tilling²

Under-tilling Problem	Description	References
Soil Compaction	If the soil is not tilled for extended periods, it can become compacted, especially in areas with heavy equipment traffic. Compacted soil can restrict root	Badalíková, 2009

	growth, reduce water infiltration, and limit soil aeration	
Weed Infestation	Tilling can be a way to control weeds by burying their seeds and disrupting their growth. Without adequate tilling, some farms might face increased weed pressures, leading to competition for nutrients, water, and light thereby increasing chemicals usage	Gruber and Claupein, 2009
Pest Issues	Certain pests, like cereal aphids and some soil-borne diseases, can thrive in undisturbed soils. Regular tilling can help in reducing their populations	Hesler and Breg, 2003
Limited Soil Warming	Tilled soil tends to warm up faster in the spring than untilled soil. This can be crucial in cooler climates where a faster soil warm-up can benefit early-planted crops	Johnston et al., 2018
Issues with Seedbed Preparation	Tilling can create a fine, crumbly seedbed ideal for seed germination and root growth. Without tilling, the seedbed might not be as conducive to germination, especially for certain crops	Winkler et al., 2022
Nutrient Stratification	Continuous no-till or minimal tilling can lead to the stratification of certain nutrients, especially phosphorus and potassium, near the soil surface. This could affect nutrient availability for deeply rooted crops	Lupwayi et al., 2006
Surface Water & Fertilizer Runoff	In certain scenarios, especially if the soil is compacted, water may not infiltrate the soil as efficiently. This can lead to increased surface water runoff, carrying with it soil particles, nutrients, and agrochemicals	Haigh and Sansom, 2007

While some of these problems may look miniscule under the lens of an individual farmer with workarounds in place for several of these, the collective environmental impact of over-tilling and under-tilling are massive and cannot be ignored, thus prompting the need for determining optimal tilling levels. In addition, fertilizer optimization is suggested during tilling so as to

ensure nutrients are incorporated in the soil effectively, and to prevent nutrient runoffs and consequently preserving soil health (Zhao et al., 2023).

Organizations have made an attempt to automate different aspects of agriculture. For example, John Deere is launching an autonomous tractor to till, plant seed, and harvest using advanced navigation controls for field boundaries, turn automation, camera-based harvest automation and such (<https://www.deere.com/en/autonomous/>). While the focus has been on labor cost reduction and productivity improvement, yield maximization, and efficiency gains through automation, not much research has gone into minimizing long-term environmental impact, such as optimizing tilling, fertilizer usage and such.

Similarly, significant research exists in the field of soil erosion. Models such as Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation 2 (RUSLE2) estimate the amount of soil loss from rill and interrill erosion due to rainfall. RUSLE2 was developed jointly by the USDA-Agricultural Research Service (ARS), the USDA-Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS), and the University of Tennessee and was written primarily to guide conservation planning, inventory erosion rates and estimate sediment delivery. While this erosion prediction tool is used by NRCS staff for conservation planning, Farm Bill Programs, inventories, and estimating sediment production for watershed structures, limited progress has been made in applying these to the day to day practices of agriculture by farmers. (<https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/about-rusle2-technology>)

2. METHODS

The fully automated tilling and soil enrichment system has 3 key sets of inputs that are leveraged by the core algorithm:

Input Set 1: Tilling level (detection using a Machine learning model based system)

Input Set 2: Soil parameter sensor module with IOT devices to measure soil moisture, soil nutrient levels, soil temperature, and field slope angle

Input Set 3: External data on rain, wind speed forecast, atmospheric temperature, soil type, and crop type

This solution is visually shown in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1 Solution Overview

2.1 Input Set 1: Tilling level detection

Tilling levels are determined by farmers today based on observation of the tilled field and experience. There are no automated methods that exist to determine tilling levels. Hence this system has been developed involving a camera picture input fed through a neural networks based machine learning model that has been trained to detect level of tilling at a high accuracy level.

Tilled soil usually has several distinctive features that can help detect the level; and intensity of tilling performed as below in *Table 3*:

Table 3
Features of Tilled Soil

Features	Description
Texture	The texture of tilled soil will generally be looser and finer, as the process breaks up compacted soil and clumps
Color	The presence of organic matter makes the top layer of soil often darker. However, tilling mixes this layer with the subsoil, thereby making it lighter in color as compared to tilled soil

Crop Residue	Tilled soil often has less visible debris (like crop residue, leaves or sticks) on the surface because the tilling process incorporates this material into the soil
Soil Displacement Width	Soil displacement width could be a good proxy for determining the tilling type and depth of the plough or tiller used.
Depth of Ridges in the Soil	The depth of ridges or lines in soil can often indicate the type and level of tilling performed

The 5 features above are further illustrated in *Figure 2* below.

Figure 2
Soil Features

Data collection process:

One way of collecting data in the form of images of tilled areas is to directly capture images from actual fields. However, this was practically too difficult given that fields only had a certain intensity of tilling at any time, and capturing data from multiple fields across all 7 tilling levels was unfathomable. Hence it was necessary to set up a simulation of a tilled field on a smaller scale in planting beds. Given the broader scope of research with soil nutrient enrichment and the

associated prototype, non-nutrient soil had to be used in the planting beds. The planting beds were filled with up to 18 inches of non-nutrient soil to simulate different tilling intensities (Figure 3).

Figure 3
Planting Beds for simulating tilling

Tilling intensities were determined based on standardized Soil Tilling Intensity Rating (STIR) guidance levels (Soil Tillage Intensity Rating STIR, 2020; nres.usda.gov). Seven different tilling levels were deduced from the guidance levels based on popular tilling practices as well as to allow for adequate distinguishing features across tilling levels. This ensured that the models recognized broader varieties of tilling across tilling depths.

The 7-point reference scale based on the above is detailed in *Table 4* below (DeJong-Hughes, 2022; Hanna et al., 1995; Claassen et al., 2018).

Table 4
Tilling Level Rating

Tilling Rating	Type of Tilling	Depth	Crop Residue
1	No Till	0 inches	100% coarse
2	Strip Till Coulter	5 - 7 inches	75% coarse and fine
3	Vertical Tillage	1 - 4 inches	60-80% fine
4	Tandem Disk	2 - 4 inches	30%+ fine
5	Disc Tillage	6 - 8 inches	15-30% fine
6	Chisel Plow	6 - 8 inches	15-30% coarse

To replicate the different tilling types, depths, and displacement widths, a variety of tools were put to use, including shovels of different sizes and shapes, rotating discs, and rakers. Hay and straw of varying lengths and granularity were used as crop residue.

In order to adequately train the machine learning model to recognize these 7 tilling levels, over 1000 images were captured using a 12 Megapixel camera mounted at a standard height range of 12 inches to 14 inches above the planting beds. To standardize the images fed as input, the height and zoom levels of the images were kept constant throughout the image capture process of the tilled field. Illustrative images of various tilling levels are shown below in *Figure 4*.

Figure 4 - Tilling Level Sample Images

The images were also validated for the tilling type and level by farmers, as a second level of assurance.

Machine Learning Models

To adequately evaluate the images for the 6 distinctive soil features described above, several machine learning (ML) model algorithms were evaluated. The “You Only Look Once” or YOLO

algorithm was evaluated and was found to be more effective for object detection. However, for image classification, the accuracy of YOLO models were not up to par. Similarly, the Open Source Computer Vision Library (OpenCV) was evaluated and found to be more effective for real-time object detection and image processing in lower accuracy use cases. Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based algorithms are Deep Learning algorithms using neural networks to process and recognize images and are designed to automatically and adaptively learn spatial hierarchies of features from input images. CNNs are made up of several layers - convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. Each layer extracts different features from the input images to aid with classification. CNNs typically provide high accuracy in image classification types of tasks and can be fine-tuned for specific applications.

Given these advantages, CNN was found to be the most appropriate machine learning algorithm to use for the tilling level determination, based on image processing. To build the CNN model, Tensorflow and Python were used along with NumPy and Keras for image processing.

A prerequisite to processing images through CNN is to standardize the image size. In this case, NumPy and Keras were used to standardize the images to 256 pixels x 256 pixels size with each pixel having its own RGB value. This was done to optimize the computational resources and reduce training time. In addition, prior to each epoch of training, a random transformation was applied using NumPy, CV2, and Keras to each image with respect to zoom level, image cropping, image rotation, and image mirroring to reduce model overfitting and to ensure the model detects the correct tilling related features in the image.

CNN models typically require several layers to be defined as follows:

Convolutional Layers

These layers apply a number of filters to the input. Each filter activates certain features from the input, like edges, textures, or more complex patterns in deeper layers. Convolution involves the element-wise multiplication of the filter matrix with the input matrix (a portion of the image) followed by a summation, as expressed in *Equation 1* below. In this model, three convolutional layers were defined, each with 32, 64, and 128 filters respectively, with each filter of size 3 pixels x 3 pixels.

Equation 1 - Convolution Operation

$$(f * g)(t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\tau) g(t - \tau) d\tau$$

Pooling Layers

Pooling (usually max pooling) reduces the spatial dimensions (height and width) of the input volume for the next convolutional layer. It helps reduce computation and parameters and controls overfitting by providing an abstracted form of the representation. This model uses three max pooling layers in between the convolutional layers.

Fully Connected Layers

These layers are traditional feed-forward neural network layers where every input is connected to every output (dense layer). They are typically placed toward the end of CNN architectures to perform classification based on the features extracted and processed by convolutional and pooling layers. In this model, two fully connected layers with sizes 256 and 512 neurons were used.

Output Layer

The output layer typically uses a softmax function, as expressed in *Equation 2* below, for multi-class classification tasks, which provides a probability distribution among the various class labels. The final output layer for this model is of size 7 neurons and uses the softmax function (Gold et al., 1996).

Equation 2 - Softmax Function Equation

$$\text{softmax}(x_i) = \frac{e^{x_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^n e^{x_j}} \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n$$

The detailed layers are described below in *Figure 5*.

Figure 5 - Convolutional Neural Network Architecture

Activation Function

Each of this model’s convolutional layers and fully connected layers use the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function, as expressed in *Figure 6*, which helps introduce non-linearity, allowing the network to learn more complex patterns. (Agarap, 2019)

Figure 6 - ReLU Equation and Graph

Adam optimization algorithm, as expressed in *Equation 3*, was used with a learning rate of 0.0001 and the sparse categorical cross entropy was used for the loss function (Kingma et al., 2015). The low learning rate was used to avoid overfitting of the model and to maximize accuracy. The model was run for 75 epochs as part of the training process aiding to a high level of accuracy.

Equation 3 - Adam Optimization Algorithm Equation

$$\nu_t = \beta_1 * \nu_{t-1} - (1 - \beta_1) * g_t$$

$$s_t = \beta_2 * s_{t-1} - (1 - \beta_2) * g_t^2$$

$$\Delta\omega_t = -\eta \frac{\nu_t}{\sqrt{s_t + \epsilon}} * g_t$$

$$\omega_{t+1} = \omega_t + \Delta\omega_t$$

η : Initial Learning rate

g_t : Gradient at time t along ω^j

ν_t : Exponential Average of gradients along ω_j

s_t : Exponential Average of squares of gradients along ω_j

β_1, β_2 : Hyperparameters

2.2 Input Set 2 - Soil Parameter Sensors

The second set of inputs involve a set of sensors and IOT devices to measure key soil and field parameters as described below.

Soil Moisture Sensor

Soil moisture is considered to be the single most important factor contributing to soil compaction (Bravo et al., 2016). Heavy clay content soils are particularly vulnerable to severe compaction under wet conditions. Hence it is important to measure soil moisture content prior to tilling to ensure the soil is not too wet. A Capacitive Soil Moisture Sensor has been used to measure soil moisture.

The capacitive moisture sensor works like a capacitor. The water in the earth changes the capacitor's capacity. By measuring the charge and discharge time, it determines the soil moisture level.

NPK Sensor

Soil nutrient levels determine the need for tilling as well as the level of tilling needed. Similarly, the amount of fertilizer needed is determined by the existing nutrient levels in the soil. In this case, a JXCT soil NPK sensor has been used as it is suitable for detecting the content of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) in the soil, and judges the fertility of the soil by detecting the conductivity transformation caused by different nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium concentrations in the soil (Bellosta-Diest et al., 2022). This is being fed as a key input into the algorithm used.

Soil Temperature

Tilling the soil can have a significant impact on soil temperature, an important factor for seed germination and plant growth. Tilling generally tends to increase the soil temperature in spring and decrease it during fall (Moroizumi et al., 2002). Hence it is important to measure soil temperature prior to tilling. To measure the soil temperature, a Bojack DS18B20 soil temperature probe is used.

Gyroscope for Field Slope Measurement

Field slope is important to measure before tilling as it impacts soil erosion and runoff. The higher the slope of the field, the greater the runoff and erosion risk. Tilling on a sloped field further increases the amount of runoff and erosion and hence the slope of the field is a critical factor to consider while determining tilling intensity (Rehman et al., 2015). In this case, the MPU-6050 gyroscope is used in order to measure the slope of the field.

2.3 Input Set 3 - External factors

In addition to the inputs described above, a few other external factors that impact tilling and fertilizer levels need to be considered and fed as inputs to the algorithm. The key external inputs are described below:

Rain Forecast

While tilling just prior to rain can incorporate moisture into the soil and help distribute nutrients in the soil, the negative effects need to be considered. Tilling the soil just prior to rain can cause soil erosion, nutrient leaching, soil compaction, and waterlogging (Ta et al., 2020). These negative effects need to be carefully considered, thus making rain forecast an important input parameter in tilling decisions.

Wind Forecast

Tilling loosens soil and breaks up soil aggregates and disrupts the soil structure, making fine soil particles more prone to being picked up and carried away by wind. Tilling often involves removing crop residues and other vegetative cover that protect the soil surface. Without this protective layer, the soil is more exposed to wind. Tilled soil tends to dry out faster, and dry soil is more susceptible to wind erosion than moist soil (Chen et al., 2022). Hence heavy wind forecast prior to tilling needs to be considered as a decision factor.

Atmospheric Temperature

Similar to soil temperature that was discussed in the section above, atmospheric temperature needs to be considered prior to tilling as well. Higher atmospheric temperatures generally result in warmer soil conditions (Jian et al., 2021). Tilling under warm conditions can be effective for soil aeration and breaking up compacted layers. However, tilling in excessively warm and dry

conditions can lead to rapid soil moisture loss, which can be detrimental to soil health and microbial activity. In colder climates or during colder seasons, the soil tends to be harder and more compact, making tilling more challenging. Tilling frozen or very cold soil can be ineffective and may harm soil structure, leading to issues like clumping. Tilling too early in spring, when the soil is still cold and wet, can also compact the soil and create clods that are difficult to break down.

Soil Type

The tilling intensity will differ based on soil type and so will the key features of the soil (Rhoton et al., 1993). This will also impact the ability to detect tilling intensity and level. For the purposes of this study, the soil type has been limited to loamy, given the experiment was performed with loamy soil in the planting beds and machine learning model has been trained based on the same.

Crop Type

Crops require varying intensities of tilling based on the type. For the purposes of this study, four different crop types have been taken into account - Row crops, Root Crops, Small Grains, and Vegetables. (Wortmann et al., 2009; Yalcin et al., 2005; Barakat et al., 2020; Love, 1986)

2.4 Algorithm

The three sets of inputs are put through a detailed algorithm programmed in Python code to determine the 2 key outputs - Tilling level and Fertilizer quantity to dispense. For each of the input parameters evaluated, upper and lower value limits were determined as described below to make it a fully functional logic.

Rain Forecast

Rain is a major factor and reason for soil erosion and nutrient wash off after tilling. The algorithm takes this as input and assesses rain over 25 mm h⁻¹ in the immediate 3 days following the day of evaluation (Shipitalo et al., 2000).

Field Slope

The runoff and erosion risks are much higher with tilling on a sloped field as opposed to a level field and erosion could be caused by wind as well as rain. It is difficult for equipment to operate on fields with slope higher than 5% grade. While slope <1% is considered relatively flat with least runoff risks, tilling intensity needs to be reduced for slope between 1% and 5% to reduce runoff risks. The recommendation is to not till the field if the slope is >5% given the soil erosion and loss is over 24% (Rehman et al., 2015; Lindstrom et al., 1990).

Wind Speed Forecast

With the standard categorizations of wind speed based on the Beaufort wind scale, levels 1 (calm) through 4 (moderate breeze) were considered to be safe after tilling with minimal to no soil disturbance while level 5 and above could cause soil disturbance based on the definition of wind rating scales on the Beaufort scale (Delmar-Morgan, 2010). However, for slopy fields, caution was taken to assess levels 0 to 3 as safe.

Soil Temperature

Soil temperature is an important factor to consider prior to tilling given that tilling when soil is very hot could drain soil moisture quickly rendering the soil dry. Similarly tilling when soil is very cold hinders root growth. Optimal range of soil temperature for tilling is between 6°C to 24°C (Dubetz et al., 1961). The algorithm uses this range to determine the min and max temperatures.

Atmospheric Temperature Forecast

As discussed in sections above, given that atmospheric temperature has a direct impact on soil temperature (Jian et al., 2021), tilling in hot weather (>24°C) and in cold weather (<6°C) are not recommended (Dubetz et al., 1961). However, with adequate soil moisture, tilling might still be acceptable as the risk of soil dry out is lower.

Soil Moisture

Tilling while soil is very moist causes compaction, which is not desirable for cultivation. Moisture levels from 10% to 30% have been considered to be appropriate for tilling, with 20% being the optimal level of soil moisture for loamy soil (Cardei et al., 2020).

Crop Type

The needs around tilling intensities and types vary based on the crop type. A standardized chart as below in *Table 5* was used to determine tilling needs.

Table 5
Tilling Level Rating

Crop Type	Tilling Intensity	Reference
Row Crops	Level 5	Wortmann et al., 2009
Small Grains	Level 4	Yalcin et al., 2005
Root Crops	Level 7	Barakat et al., 2020
Vegetables	Level 2	Love, 1986

Soil Nutrient Level (NPK value)

Soil nutrient requirements vary by crop type. By assessing the current NPK value of the soil and the required levels, the fertilizer quantities were determined through a calibration method that computes the difference between current NPK values and required NPK values and NPK levels per gram of fertilizer dispensed.

Using the above factors and tolerance limits, the algorithm has been defined along with the detailed logic used across the entire input set, as described in *Figure 7*.

Figure 7 - Algorithm

2.5 Prototype

To thoroughly test the concepts discussed along with all the input sets and desired outputs, a prototype was developed. The core modules of the prototype are as discussed below:

Self-driving Vehicle

A self-driving vehicle was designed and built from scratch to control the motion and speed as needed, depending on whether input measurements were taken or output actions such as tilling and/or fertilizer dispensing were carried out.

The vehicle was designed and 3D printed at home using a modularized design/build process, given the extreme customizations that were required to make all the functionality work. The primary drive system consisted of two 12V DC motors 0.6A with 30RPM speed attached to the two rear wheels. The DC motors were controlled by an Arduino IDE compatible ESP32 microcontroller. 12mm tires were used for ease of navigation on the soil bed. All the input and output units were mounted on this main vehicle for ease of operation and control. An image of the vehicle is shown in *Figure 8* below.

Figure 8 - Vehicle

Camera Module (Input set 1)

A camera module was mounted on the vehicle at a height of 12 inches consistent with the height at which the images were captured for training the machine learning model. A OV2640 2MP camera with a built-in 520 KB SRAM and 8MB external PSRAM was used and was connected to an Arduino module to automate the camera control. An image of the camera module is shown in *Figure 9* below.

Figure 9 - Camera Module

Sensor Module (Input Set 2)

An automated sensor module was mounted to the vehicle and with capability to plunge all the sensors up to 6 inches down automatically to take the necessary measurements. The sensors that were mounted to the module board included Soil Moisture Sensor, NPK Sensor, Soil Temperature sensor, and a Gyroscope for Field Slope Measurement. The module board was 3D printed to hold all the sensors in place. An ESP32 microcontroller was used to control the sensors and capture sensor inputs. Another ESP32 controlled the vertical movement of the sensor module allowing it to plunge down into the soil. To enable this vertical or linear movement, a Scotch Yoke mechanism (also called a slotted link mechanism) was used as it converts the rotational motion of a stepper motor (in this case, ULN2003 5V Stepper Motor) into a linear motion through a reciprocating motion mechanism. An image of the sensor module is shown in *Figure 10* below.

Figure 10 - Sensor Module

Tiller Module (Output 1)

An independently operating and automated tiller module with two types of tillers was 3D printed to suit the level of customization required. The first automated tiller was a 4 inch deep moldboard plough that could be lowered and raised automatically based on an ESP32 microcontroller. The second automated tiller was a 2 inch deep disk tiller which could also be lowered and raised automatically and controlled by the same ESP32 microcontroller. Both the tillers are controlled by independent ULN2003 5V stepper motors.

An image of the tiller module is shown in *Figure 11* below.

Figure 11 - Tiller Module

Fertilizer Dispensing Module (Output 2)

As the second output module, the fertilizer dispenser could automatically and independently dispense desired quantities of fertilizer as determined by the core algorithm. The mechanism used for this module included a ULN2003 5V stepper motor with its rotation counts determined by the core algorithm controlled by ESP32 and Arduino module. The motor connected to a circular disc with a small segment of opening enabled measured quantities of fertilizer in powder form to be dispensed depending on the number of rotations of the disc.

An image of the fertilizer dispensing module is shown in *Figure 12* below.

Figure 12 - Fertilizer Dispensing Module

2.6 Simulation Setup

In addition to the algorithm validation, a simulation method has been used to validate the effectiveness of optimal tilling and fertilizer quantity usage. This is accomplished by comparing

a conventionally tilled farm against a farm that is tilled according to the algorithm’s output. This was setup in the Agricultural Production Systems sIMulator (APSIM) (Keating et al., 2003). A 30 year weather dataset of Iowa was taken and used on both farms to ensure consistency. The crop type of the farm was corn, and tilling intensity was the only parameter that was changed between the farms. Default settings were used for the rest of the parameters, based on the actual conditions in Iowa during the 30 year period.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Machine Learning Based Tilling Level Determination

The Convolutional Neural Network based ML model that was trained using the sample images was put to test using test data as a new set of images captured from the tilled plant bed. The model was able to classify the images with over 97% accuracy level. While the positive test scenarios included appropriately tilled samples conforming to specific tilling levels, negative and alternate test images were also captured that included non-calibrated levels that were in between levels 4 and 5 as well as in between levels 6 and 7. Even in these cases, the model was able to determine the tilling levels to either the prior or next level at 90% accuracy, with incorrect predictions falling within a margin of error of 1 level. This result further solidifies the model’s ability to identify specific soil properties in determining tilling intensity.

The accuracy measure of the output based on tests performed is as shown below in *Table 6*:

Table 6 - Machine Learning Model Testing and Accuracy

Test Performed	Accuracy
Total Accuracy on training data	100%
Total Accuracy on 140 Images of unseen test data	97.1429%
Total Accuracy within 1 level margin of error on 140 Images of unseen test data	98.5714%
Accuracy on identifying images between tilling levels 4 and 5 (only one level deviation for incorrect predictions)	90%
Accuracy on identifying images between tilling levels 6 and 7 (only one level deviation for incorrect predictions)	90%

Tilling Level and Fertilizer Level algorithm Output

The algorithm testing involved simulating several tilling levels as input and NPK values for soil as inputs along with a variety of combinations of input parameters to represent the different decision triggers for the algorithm to consider. Some of the external input parameters such as atmospheric temperature, rain forecast, wind speed forecast, Soil type and Crop type were simulated to feed the algorithm appropriately so as to cover the multitude of scenarios to test the algorithm. The algorithm successfully passed the testing for all the combinations of inputs, providing the desired output.

A sample of testing with different sets of inputs and desired outputs is shown in *Table 7* below.

Table 7 - Algorithm Testing - Input and Output

Rain Forecast (Next 3 days)	Field Slope	Wind Speed Forecast Level	Air Temp Forecast (°C)	Soil Temp (°C)	Soil Moisture	Crop Type	NPK Value	Current Tilling Level	Output*
0mm	0.5%	3	20	20	21%	Row	3, 5, 5	3	TL=4 FZ=5
30mm	0.5%	3	20	20	21%	Row	3, 5, 5	3	TL=0 FZ=0
5mm	2%	3	20	20	21%	Row	3, 5, 5	3	TL=3 FZ=5
0mm	0%	5	20	20	21%	Row	3, 5, 5	2	TL=0 FZ=0
0mm	0%	2	5	8	21%	Row	3, 5, 5	2	TL=0 FZ=0
0mm	0%	2	35	22	21%	Row	3, 5, 5	2	TL=0 FZ=0
0mm	0%	2	20	18	50%	Row	3, 5, 5	2	TL=0 FZ=0
0mm	0%	2	20	18	22%	Root	3, 5, 5	2	TL=6 FZ=5

* TL = Tilling level recommended and FZ = Fertilizer level recommended (mg/kg of soil)

Simulation Testing Output

The algorithm was further tested using a simulation that was run for 30 years. The results are outlined in *Figure 13*

Figure 13 - Simulation Results

A global adoption of the proposed end-to-end solution has the potential to reduce runoffs by up to 86%, carbon emissions on the farm by 57%, and fertilizer usage by up to 43%, as shown in the 30 year simulation. This proves the effectiveness and rigor of the algorithm in determining optimal tilling intensities through automated, scientific means.

Prototype Testing Output

The prototype with the vehicle, sensor module, tiller module, and fertilizer dispensing module was tested for the combinations of input as specified in the section above to ensure that the output calibrations for tilling levels for the tilling system and the fertilizer dispensing system matched the configurations. The prototype successfully passed the testing and produced the desired results, thus acting as a fully functional and demonstrable model of the entire set of inputs and outputs discussed in this study.

Following the successful tractor prototype testing, a stationary version of the prototype was developed with the camera and sensor modules along with a display unit to show status. This

prototype was then successfully replicated and deployed in 155 farms across Belgium, the Netherlands, France, USA, and India. *Figure 14* shows the stationary version of the prototype.

Figure 14 - Stationary Prototype

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study demonstrated that first and foremost, a fully automated scientific approach could be taken in measuring the existing tilling intensities of a field. Then, it illustrated that this data could be combined with soil sensor data and other external weather and crop type data using a robust algorithm to determine key outputs such as optimal tilling intensity and fertilizer level. The simulation compared the effects of applying the optimal tilling intensity to fields against the conventional tillage intensities and proved that significant reductions in soil erosion, runoff, carbon release and fertilizer usage could be accomplished. The working prototype brings it all together through a fully automated tilling solution that could be evaluated further for full-size prototyping in the field. Automated solutions enabling optimal tilling could result in far-reaching environmental benefits that are multi-fold as described in this study. Hence, it is highly

recommended to develop this prototype into a full scale automated solution that could transform the industry and the environment.

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